

From Territorial Identity to Territorial Branding: Tourism-led Revitalization of Minor Historic Towns in Reggio Calabria

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Abstract

Reggio Calabria in Southern Italy boasts many well-preserved minor³⁸ historic towns (MHTs) of Greek origins. These MHTs are characterized by a strong territorial identity with small-sized centers, often isolated from urban basins. However, these MHTs suffer from continuing degradation due to depopulation and stagnating local socio-economic development (LSED). This article, grounded on an asset-based endogenous approach and system-based relational approach to tourism development, maintains that tourism development is an effective tool to revitalize these towns while promoting LSED. It therefore attempts to explore a tourism-led revitalization model for MHTs where territorial identity and territorial branding are respectively fundamental assets and means. To this end, the research first investigates the constituents of territorial identity, the existing problems that the territorial identity is facing, territorial branding approaches and practices in the MHTs in relation to the two approaches to tourism development. By carrying out case studies of Penteadattilo, Riace and Belmonte, the research then analyzes how urban regeneration can contribute to territorial identity, which improves the tourist attractiveness of the MHTs. This article concludes that territorial branding and value-adding of territorial identity, promoted by regenerative interventions, help improve tourism quality and diversify tourism offer, which, in turn, results in the revitalization of the MHTs.

Keywords

Tourism; Territorial Identity; Territorial Branding; Minor Historic Towns (MHTs); Revitalization.

1. Introduction

Rural and peri-urban areas worldwide are not immune from impacts of urbanization. Urbanization, on the one hand, facilitates rural modernization, and on the other hand, triggers various problems ranging from environmental and landscape degradation, and depopulation to community exclusion. These negative transformations, hardly arguable, have undermined local socio-economic development (LSED) in rural and peri-urban areas. In facing these particular issues, different approaches have emerged to stimulate LSED in rural and peri-urban areas. Among these approaches, rural tourism is utilized, yet tends to encounter obstacles. A common problem found is “the absence of a rural tourism policy, which has the effect of marginalizing small-scale providers from regional and national promotional efforts” (McCool, 2015a: 7). In contrast, tourism activities in rural areas have been criticized as “insensitive to indigenous community cultural norms and values, in other cases as producing low quality jobs, and in still others leading to unacceptable environmental impacts” (*ibid*). To mitigate negative externalities tourism may bring about in rural and peri-urban areas, an endogenous approach, centered on local capital and assets, starts to emerge. Cawley, for example, applies a model of integrated

³⁸ “Minor” refers to their small sized centers, a connotative attribute to signify territorial entities that do not meet requirements of large and medium cities, but still go in an integrated manner intended by their territory (Lauria, 2009).

rural tourism (IRT) as a way of adding value locally. In this model, producers are encouraged to change their role from mere cultivators to conservators of the countryside, while seeking supplementary source of income through the adaptation of land, labor, and capital to new uses, such as tourism (Cawley, 2010). Agro-tourism best describes this place-based value-adding process, which demands a reorientation of agricultural output markets and diversification of the rural economy by adding value to the local nature and landscape and all kinds of other local resources (Cristóvão *et al.*, 1994).

In addition to an endogenous focus on capital and assets, there is also a relational approach that pays increasing attention to the linkage between a certain locality and its external environment. Deeming the external environment as contention, complex, uncertain and changing, McCool (2015a, 2015b), advocates a new mental model of sustainable tourism (MMST). This mental model, guided by “systems thinking”, is expected to respond to the need to reframe the role of sustainable tourism in economic development and make communities more resilient and vibrant in a turbulent and changing environment (McCool, 2015a). “Systems thinking” involves considering relationships across time, space and function (McCool, 2015b), therefore holistically conceptualizing tourism as one component of a social-ecological system (Shakia, 2015). Collaboration is supportive of “systems thinking”, since it brings out a greater integration between rural tourism and other economic sectors, thus leading to collaborative innovation (Bramwell and Lane, 2000).

Would the aforementioned two approaches to tourism development contribute to the revitalization of minor historic towns³⁹ (MHTs) in rural and peri-urban areas of the province of Reggio Calabria (hereinafter referred to as Reggio Calabria) in Southern Italy? The rationale for such a question lies in the fact that these MHTs, often isolated from the urban basins, cover extended areas, but are sparsely inhabited, economically stagnating, and physically degrading. To answer this question, the research first looks into how tourism can be promoted by adding value to territorial identity and undertaking territorial branding, through which socio-cultural capital is mobilized, while generating socio-economic benefits to boost local development. Then, the research discusses urban regeneration approaches and practices in the MHTs. Based on case studies of Pentedattilo, Riace and Belmonte, it analyzes how urban regeneration facilitates territorial branding and promotes territorial identity, therefore increasing the attractiveness of tourism.

2. Tourism in Minor Historic Towns (MHTs)

The MHTs in Reggio Calabria enjoy unique territorial identity characteristics of originality, diversity and richness, be it material and immaterial cultural heritage or landscapes. Their territorial identity, in essence, is their inherent assets and source of attractiveness, therefore they are able to fuel tourism-led local socio-economic development on the condition that there be a value-adding process in place.

³⁹ The phenomenon of “minor historical center” (cities with fewer than 10,000 inhabitants) concerns, in fact, more than six thousand of the 8,100 Italian municipalities, of which just over 5,800 have a population of less than 5,000 inhabitants, about 3,600 less than 2,000, nearly 2,000 less than 1,000, and more than eight hundred less than 500. In Calabria Region, of its 420 municipalities a little less than 400 are minor historic towns (Lauria, 2009).

2.1. Territorial Identity as Assets

Mostly of Greek origins, the MHTs in the province of Reggio Calabria in Southern Italy manifest unique and distinct territorial identity. Territorial identity is often believed to be a contributing factor of local development, since it influences local evolutionary processes, while shaping the potential of endogenous development of territories and enhancing territorial cohesion (Lee *et al.*, 2005; Ray, 2006; Veneri, 2011; Orduna Allegrini, 2012). However, the definition/understanding of territorial identity tends to be subjective. According to Banini and Pollice (2015), territorial identity is a dynamic, open and participatory social process, gaining its shape from the institutional, economic and organizational environment (Vázquez-Barquero, 2003), which marks the “social construction”⁴⁰ of the territory (2015: 5). While Roca *et al.* (2016) stress the natural, economic, societal and cultural features of territorial identity, Camagni (2006) argues that social capital and cultural heritage are determinants of territorial identity. Veneri (2011) maintains that territorial identity has four main components: social capital, socio-cultural identity, spatial organization of activities and governance structure. This research pays special attention to the territorial identity that the MHTs in Reggio Calabria demonstrate, in considering territorial identity, as a totality of the material and the immaterial that encompasses cultural heritage (both material and immaterial), landscapes, language, environment and climate, peculiar agricultural products, and humanity (territorial temperament and *zeitgeist* for example). All of these are constituents of the social and cultural capital and natural resource of the MHTs. Territorial identity, in this sense, refers to all forms of capital and assets that can be mobilized to catalyze local socio-economic development.

Although boasting a strong, highly potential territorial identity, such as unique landscape, tangible and intangible heritage, living traditions and rituals, peculiar agricultural products, etc., the MHTs are faced with many problems (Figures 1, 2), such as abandonment, depopulation, degrading built environment and lagging facilities and services.

Figure 1 - Abandoned houses in Pentedattilo.
Source: Ou Yapeng (2016)

Figure 2 - The abandoned Palazzo del Giudice in Belmonte Calabro.
Source: Ou Yapeng (2016)

⁴⁰ See the Concept Note of the 3rd World Forum of Local Economic Development (2015).

Amaro (2009) reckons that the abandonment in MHTs is due to a lack of investment attention or economic processes, which leads to a “traumatic” result. Indeed, this territorial trauma largely results from drastic economic change that has interrupted an ancient culture deeply-rooted in the land, following mass migration and displacement along the coastal areas. As for the political-economic environment in Calabria Region, Reggio Calabria offers a representative picture: it has long been heavily dependent on public transfers, while undergoing fragmentation of the urban social structure. Both factors explain “the absence of strong local actors and the protracted subordination of local elites to exogenous agency, i.e. choices and actions determined outside the region” (Barillà, 2013: 256).

Taking into account the characteristics of the MHTs’ endogenous territorial identity and exogenous political-economic conditions, the authors maintain that the asset-based endogenous approach and system-based relational approach can serve as guiding principles to formulate and operate tourism activities so as to lever LSED. However, it is worth noting that the functionality of the two approaches depends largely on whether proactive territorial branding practices are in place so as to add value to the territorial identity.

2.2. Territorial Branding as a Value-adding Tool

Currently, competitiveness remains a keyword in the European Union Rural Development Policy (RDP), which can be seen from the objectives of the ongoing rural development programs for the period 2014-2020⁴¹ and previous period 2007-2013⁴². RDP also stresses the importance of achieving a balanced territorial development of rural economies and communities (2014-2020), enhancing the quality of life in rural areas and promoting diversification of economic activities (2007-2013) (European Commission, 2011). Rural areas are therefore conceptualized as “multifunctional spaces” that satisfy purposes of recreation, environmental, landscape protection, and economic development. This vital shift leads to an emerging *modello delle reti ecologiche*⁴³ (ecological networks model) in response to a *modello agricolo produttivista* (productivist agricultural model) in crisis (Presidency of the Council of Ministers, 2016).

Given that rural and peri-urban areas tend to possess “limited, hyper-mobile financial, human or cultural resource” (Ashworth *et al.*, 2014: 4), territorial branding (also termed as place branding) is indispensable for them to become or remain competitive. Indeed, territorial branding is a booster of competitiveness, helping places “fight in the increasingly intense arena of interplace competition” (*ibid*). Besides, territorial branding can provide strategic guidance for place development, a basis for stakeholder cooperation, solutions to practical/functional place-related problems, and opportunities to maximize positive place experience to consumers (residents, visitors, investors, etc.) (*ibid*). In addition, territorial branding can foster innovation, “a collective/interactive process, which cannot take place outside a highly and systemic dimension that favors it” (Bagautdinova, 2012: 181). It therefore can be seen that territorial

⁴¹ Foster the competitiveness of agriculture; ensure the sustainable management of natural resources, and support action over the climate; achieve a balanced territorial development of rural economies and communities, including the creation and maintenance of employment.

⁴² Increasing the competitiveness of the agricultural and forestry sector; improving the environment and countryside through support for land management; enhancing the quality of life in rural areas and promoting diversification of economic activities.

⁴³ The ecological networks model is deemed as capable of putting biodiversity and landscape at the center of land planning and management (Presidency of the Council of Ministers, 2016).

branding has both endogenous and exogenous nature: it needs to be based on a place's assets and capital while addressing its problems; and, at the meantime, it needs to have a "systems thinking" mindset. This nature suggests its capability to support the asset-based endogenous approach and system-based relational approach to tourism development.

According to Bagautdinova (2012), the result of territorial branding in facilitating tourism-led development practices is determined by the value of territory, the level of activism of its community, integrated offer of structures, services and goods for different categories of tourists, and the accessibility to the territory and its excellences. The authors, however, maintain that the effectiveness of territorial branding depends on whether the territorial identity is fully mobilized through a value-adding process.

Presently, the MHTs in Reggio Calabria are undergoing various territorial branding practices predominantly with an endogenous approach, while exogenous approach is an emerging tool. Endogenous territorial branding is aimed at adding value to the MHTs' cultural assets and natural resources, with a pronounced focus on their material and immaterial cultural heritage, as well as agricultural products. Folkloric festivals serve as an important medium for this kind of territorial branding. One good place-based practice is the *Paeleariza*, an ethno-cultural-musical festival which takes place annually in the Grecanic areas (*aree grecaniche*) of Reggio Calabria and began in 1997. *Paeleariza* always takes place in public spaces (squares, streets, historic buildings, theatrical and entertainment areas) of numerous historic towns/villages of Municipalities of the Grecanic areas, such as Bova, Cardeto, Condofuri, San Lorenzo, Africo, Roghudi, Palizzi, etc. It uses minimal staging to take full advantage of urban spaces, squares, facades of historic buildings or the surrounding landscapes, which are all integral elements of the open air setting. Indeed, the soul of the festival lies in a seamless integration between the content and cultural and environmental containers, and between the material and the immaterial. Over the years, by adding value to the territorial identity, *Paeleariza* has never stopped innovation. For example, in the 2015 edition, it created the summer school of Calabrian Greek (*lingua grecanica*) organized by the *Associazione Scuola Estiva di Lingua Greka di Calabria* located in Bova Marina. Today, this festival has already become a business card of ethno-cultural tourism of the whole area, distinguishing itself for its ability to keep alive the folklore of its territory while innovating the traditional representations of territorial identity and adapting to changing times. In 2011, *Paeleariza* was nominated by the Italian Ministry of Tourism as "Heritage of Italy" for its dedication to cultural events that contribute to enhancing the image of Italy and generating new tourism. There are various *sagra* festivals dedicated to promoting local gastronomic specialties while aiming at visitors and tourists.

During the territorial branding process, community-led institutions, such as *pro loco*, cultural associations and inter-community networks play a significant role. *Pro loco* (Latin phrase which means "in favor of the place") are grass-roots organizations dedicated to promoting local tourism. Different from publicly financed organizations such as the *Azienda di Promozione Turistica* (Agency of Tourism Promotion) or the *Ufficio di Informazione e Accoglienza Turistica* (Office of Tourist Information and Reception), *pro loco* are non-profit entities. By means of adding value to the territorial identity, they are aimed at triggering tourism-related activities and improving the quality of life for the local population. For this purpose, *pro loco*, when developing tourism activities, attach great importance to typical enogastronomic products and local handicrafts, folkloric traditions, cultural and landscape heritage, etc. In doing so, *pro loco*

help form a “double beneficial effect”, namely, the initiatives meant to improve physical conditions of the place and the living conditions of local population coincide with the initiatives that lay the necessary foundation for a quality tourism.

According to Shakia (2015), bridging social capital has a positive impact on tourism-led local development, namely, extra-community networks is considered as a growth booster. The existence of social capital within destination communities can promote the sustainability of tourism development. Considered a contributing factor to the building of bridging social capital, exogenous territorial branding approach starts to gain popularity in recent years. Often in the form of extra-community networks and/or public-private partnerships, territorial branding in this case is aimed at facilitating inter-territorial exchange and collaboration. For example, the private agency *Parco Culturale della Calabria Greca*^{44,45} (Cultural Park of the Greek Calabria), dedicated to the promotion of sustainable tourism, constructs a network involving about 20 tourism operators, 8 cultural associations located in different towns and villages in the Greek Calabria, and the Academy of Fine Arts of Reggio Calabria. In this sense, it is clear that the agency adopts a concept based on “systems thinking”, a broad idea of territoriality, which includes the entire Greek Calabria.

Despite the above-mentioned territorial branding approaches and activities, a considerable portion of the MHTs’ highly potential territorial identity remains with idle assets. More work needs to be done to add value to their unique landscapes, tangible and intangible heritage, peculiar agricultural products, etc. In the following part, the authors discuss how urban regeneration practices can help mobilize the idle assets while increasing the tourism attractiveness of the MHTs.

3. Urban Regeneration in Minor Historic Towns (MHTs)

Given the degrading built environment even the formation of “ghost towns” following continuous depopulation in the MHTs, urban regeneration proves to be a badly needed tool to revitalize them by promoting their territorial identity and territorial branding process. Through continuous regeneration, the MHTs can heighten their tourist attractiveness, which demands the coincidence of economic and cultural activities in civic design since the two are mutually impacting (Dix, 1995). A common goal of urban regeneration is “a lasting improvement in the economic, physical, social and environmental condition of an area that has been subject to change” (Roberts and Sykes, 2000: 296). For this goal, various urban regeneration approaches have been experimented in the MHTs in Reggio Calabria. In the coming section, the research carries out three case studies demonstrating different regeneration methods: the reuse and repurpose approach in Pentedattilo, the social constructivist approach in Riace, and the beautification approach in Belmonte Calabro⁴⁶.

⁴⁴ Greek Calabria (Calabria Greca) refers to a strip of territory of about 500 km² that ranges from the Aspromonte mountains down to the Ionian Sea. This territory of Calabria is “Greek” because of its Greek legacy. Until today, the Calabrian dialect of Greek, or Greek-Bovesian, is still spoken by the elders from ancient Greek towns and villages such as Galliciano, Bova, Condofuri, Roghudi, etc.

⁴⁵ The activities of the Park are mainly in relation to sustainable tourism in Greek Calabria, cultural laboratories, multimedia library, and tourist information and reception.

⁴⁶ Different from Pentedattilo and Riace which are located in the province of Reggio Calabria, Calabria, Belmonte Calabro is located in the province of Cosenza, Calabria.

3.1. Reuse and Repurpose in Pentedattilo

The most common regeneration practice is reuse and repurpose characteristic of functional adaptation and diversification. Recycling existing assets and tourism-led development can give an impetus for improving the infrastructure and sustainability of a place (Parlewar and Fukukawa, 2006). In Pentedattilo (Figure 3), which became completely uninhabited in the mid-1960s, a long course of preventative and interventional preservation since the 1980s initiated by young people and associations has prevented the village from continuing degrading. Today, tourism plays a pivotal role in the revitalization of the “ghost village”, adding value to its regenerated physical fabric. The reuse and repurpose of its architectural heritage is mainly aimed at promoting local artisan products. This not only helps maintain the integrity of its built environment, but also creates a synergy between the economy and the culture, and between the material and immaterial of the territorial identity. Many of its abandoned houses were restored and repurposed as artisan laboratories and shops, most of which are operated by grass-roots associations. All handicrafts bear strong territorial identities. There is a laboratory dedicated to artisan products, both traditional and innovative, based on bergamot orange⁴⁷. Another laboratory of wooden handicrafts proves to be highly innovative, in that it serves as a multi-functional space: artisan and pedagogic laboratory, ethnographic museum and tourism information (Figure 4). In addition to reuse and repurpose, cultural activities also help revitalize the town. The two most influential ones are the *Paleariza* Festival every summer and the Pentedattilo Film Festival, an international short film festival between August and September.

Figure 3 - Panorama of Pentedattilo.

Source: Ou Yapeng (2016)

Figure 4 - The *Laboratorio Artigianale del Legno* in Pentedattilo, a multifunctional laboratory serving as artisan and pedagogic laboratory, ethnographic museum and tourism information.

Source: Ou Yapeng (2016)

⁴⁷ Bergamot orange is a cultural symbol of Reggio Calabria. Its production mostly is limited to the Ionian Sea coastal areas of Reggio Calabria.

3.2. Social Constructivism in Riace

The regeneration of Riace, instead, takes a social constructivist approach for its advocacy of social inclusion and social justice. Fifteen years ago, the medieval village was almost reduced to a “ghost town” due to continuous migration of the local population. Since 2004, through public and community collaboration, Riace has been a pioneer in Calabria to host refugees, a quite “revolutionary” action at that time. Then with the entry into force of the Regional Law No. 18/2009 for the welcome and integration of political refugees, more and more partially abandoned towns, among which Caulonia, Stignano and Acquaformosa, also started to repopulate themselves by resettling refugees and immigrants. The strong presence of refugees and immigrants has turned into an opportunity for the recovering of portions of the abandoned historic towns through their repopulation (Russo, 2014). In Riace, with public funding, refugees are offered the abandoned houses and training. A variety of artisan workshops were opened to refugees where they can gain professional skills, earn a wage and learn trades that are disappearing locally. The handicrafts are then sold to tourists. This Riace Model of regeneration has not only helped to solve the problem of degrading built environment of the town due to derelict buildings, but also rebuild both the town’s population and economy. In this case, social inclusion and social cohesion has transformed into bridging social capital and added value to the territorial identity while promoting local socio-economic development, hence making Riace a more livable and attractive place.

3.3. Beautification in Belmonte Calabro

Beautification is also a common regenerative practice, as Belmonte Calabro illustrates. For several decades, like numerous MHTs in Calabria, Belmonte Calabro has seen a general phenomenon of population decline, leaving the town increasingly empty. The town’s economy, besides the traditional primary sector linked to agriculture, depends to a large extent on seaside tourism on the nearby coast of the Tyrrhenian Sea in summer time.

Figure 5 - Painted stairways in Belmonte Calabro.
Source: *Ou Yapeng (2016)*

Figure 6 - Painted stairways in Belmonte Calabro.
Source: *Ou Yapeng (2016)*

This triggers a series of regeneration interventions to revitalize the town and increase its tourist attractiveness. There has been reuse and repurpose of abandoned buildings, and recently, beautification of the historic center. Major interventions are mural and stairway paintings (Figures 5, 6), green infrastructures, as well as public furnishings. The regeneration also involves the promotion of local immaterial heritage. The local association “Belmonte in Rete”, for example, organizes workshops, among many other scientific and cultural activities, where students and residents can learn about handicraft makings, such as traditional weaving.

As the cases of Belmonte, Pentedattilo, and Riace illustrate, endogenous urban regeneration of the MHTs in Calabria proves to be an effective tool to support territorial branding, making these towns and villages more attractive tourist destinations.

4. Conclusions

The minor historic towns (MHTs) in Reggio Calabria, often isolated from the urban basins, are in fact extended areas but sparsely inhabited, economically stagnating, and physically degrading. Although they boast unique and distinct territorial identities composed of material and immaterial cultural heritage, landscape, peculiar agricultural products, etc., the MHTs have seen a slow local socio-economic development (LSED). To address this development issue, the research has come up with a tourism-led revitalization model for the MHTs where territorial identity and territorial branding are respectively fundamental assets and means. Given the characteristics of the MHTs’ endogenous territorial identity and exogenous political-economic conditions, tourism development led by the asset-based endogenous approach and system-based relational approach are effective tools to revitalize these towns while leveraging LSED.

Abandonment, depopulation, degrading built environment and lagging facilities and services in MHTs as well as the unfavorable exogenous political-economic conditions altogether are undermining the territorial identity, bringing obstacles to tourism development and LSED. In response, various territorial branding practices with predominantly endogenous approach have been undertaken to promote the value-adding process of the territorial identity, transforming idle assets into active boosters of local tourist attractiveness. Endogenous urban regeneration practices characteristic of reuse and repurpose, social constructivism and beautification have contributed to the territorial branding and value-adding of the territorial identity, making the MHTs more attractive to tourists. All in all, territorial branding accompanied by value-adding of territorial identity, facilitated by regenerative interventions, helps improve the quality of tourism and diversify tourism offers, which in turn results in the revitalization of the MHTs and generates socio-economic benefits for the local population.

Due to space limitation, the paper did not discuss in depth the exogenous territorial branding practices in the MHTs of Reggio Calabria. Besides, taking into account the need of financial instruments to make any LSED initiatives socio-economically viable and sustainable, it would be desirable that the future research, on the one hand, integrate the mixed model proposed in the current research with civic crowd-funding mechanism managed by the local community to help implement LSED initiatives based on local assets. On the other hand, it would be desirable to propose for the entire province of Reggio Calabria a regional development paradigm driven by tourism-led revitalization of the MHTs. Such a paradigm, with the LSED of the MHTs

integrated into the Metropolitan City strategy⁴⁸, will help foster a synergy between urban development and rural and peri-urban development in Reggio Calabria.

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⁴⁸ The Italian Law No. 56/2014, the "Delrio Law", listed Reggio Calabria as a metropolitan city (*città metropolitana*), operative since 2015. As an administrative division, a metropolitan city is composed of a large core city and the smaller surrounding cities that are closely related to it in terms of economic activities, public services, cultural relations and territorial features.

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